
REPORT ON THE PATHWAYS FOR MUTUAL LEARNING

Transnational Level

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We want to clarify that the use of English in this Document has been checked with the online AI-enhanced tool “DeepL.com” (free versions), for improvement of the writing style and clarity. We have then reviewed the resulting contents to ensure consistency with our original texts and correspondence with the Consortium’s vision and priorities.

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Introduction

The B.RIGHT SPACES' series of transnational webinars is designed to **enrich ongoing policy conversations and participatory initiatives** taking place across the five project territories. By complementing the B.RIGHT SPACES local-level focus groups and policy debates, these sessions provide a broader framework for reflection and exchange.

At the heart of this process lies the understanding of **rights as lived experiences**, deeply influenced by local contexts, meaning that their realisation varies across different territories. This **territorial dimension of rights** suggests that their protection and promotion should not be seen as citizens' isolated demands but as **shared responsibilities**. Public authorities and other stakeholders must engage in constructive and inclusive dialogue to design the most effective ways to implement these rights in practice.

The topics

The webinar series explored how fundamental rights can move beyond formal declarations to become part of people's daily lives. Across five sessions, we examined how local actors or stakeholders, including local and regional public authorities, associations and NGOs, social economy organisations, as well as informal groups and communities, contributed to making rights tangible and accessible.

We began with the **“From Declared Rights to Lived Rights – Making Rights Real”** webinar, which introduced the idea that rights are not only legal texts but experiences shaped by local conditions. Through examples in areas such as social services and care, we reflected on the roles of different stakeholders in turning rights into concrete opportunities.

The second session, **“Rights in Peripheral Areas – Local Solutions to Reduce Inequality”** focused on the specific challenges faced by people living in disadvantaged or remote areas. We looked at how local authorities and community initiatives addressed these inequalities by developing practical, place-based responses to improve access to essential services.

In **“Education and Culture for All – Accessible and Inclusive Pathways”** we examined how education and cultural

WED, 30 APRIL 9:00 - 10:30 (CET)	<p style="text-align: center;">FROM DECLARED RIGHTS TO LIVED RIGHTS MAKING RIGHTS REAL</p> <p>This session introduces the idea that rights are not only legal declarations but experiences shaped by local contexts. Through concrete examples about access to social and community services we will explore how different stakeholders can help turn rights into real opportunities for people.</p> <p>FOCUS ON...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City of Turin and the “Case di Quartiere” network (Italy) • FISE and an exemplary MAL (Local Activity Place) from Warsaw area (Poland)
FRI, 9 MAY 9:00 - 10:30 (CET)	<p style="text-align: center;">RIGHTS IN PERIPHERAL AREAS LOCAL SOLUTIONS TO REDUCE INEQUALITY(IES)</p> <p>People living in peripheral and deprived areas often face major challenges in accessing basic rights such as healthcare, education and employment. Drawing on experiences from different territories, this session will explore how local authorities and communities can take practical steps to address these inequalities.</p> <p>FOCUS ON...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The value of networking in the experience of the Xarxa d'Espais Comunitaris in Barcelona (Spain) • The CREATIVE association supporting inclusion and employment in the peripheral “priority neighbourhoods” in Garges-lès-Gonesse (France) • Mutual support and community engagement in Rome (Italy)
FRI, 23 MAY 10:00 - 11:30 (CET)	<p style="text-align: center;">EDUCATION AND CULTURE FOR ALL ACCESSIBLE AND INCLUSIVE PATHWAYS</p> <p>Education and culture are key to citizen empowerment and inclusion, but access is not always equal. This session explores practical ways to make learning and cultural opportunities more accessible, with insights from successful local initiatives.</p> <p>FOCUS ON...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Culture and arts empowering citizens and upholding rights in the Torres Vedras municipality (Portugal) • Promoting human development in a vulnerable territory: the work of the Fondazione Hercynus Orca in Messina (Italy) • Human rights-based approach in Västra Götalandsregionen (Sweden)
FRI, 6 JUN 10:00 - 12:00 (CET)	<p style="text-align: center;">GOVERNANCE AND PARTICIPATION POLICIES THAT MAKE A DIFFERENCE</p> <p>How can local authorities put rights into action? This webinar will focus on how local authorities can make rights tangible through legal, administrative, and financial frameworks. It will also explore ways to involve civil society and marginalised groups in policy design while addressing resistance to change.</p> <p>FOCUS ON...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The shared administration of common goods and collaboration pacts promoted and supported by the Comune di Torino (Italy) • The EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) about the practical guidance on “Human rights cities in the European Union” • The initiatives of the Città Metropolitana di Roma Capitale - Ufficio di supporto alla consigliera delegata alle Pari opportunità, Politica sociale, Cultura, Partecipazione, Trasparenza e Anticorruzione • Public policies for a new democratic paradigm in the Generalitat de Catalunya (Spain)

The B.RIGHT SPACES' series of transnational webinars is designed to enrich ongoing policy conversations and participatory initiatives taking place across the project territories. By complementing local-level discussions, these sessions provide a broader framework for reflection and exchange.

At the heart of this process lies our understanding of rights as **lived experiences** with a specific territorial dimension. This approach suggests that their protection and promotion should not be seen as citizens' isolated demands but as shared responsibilities. Public authorities and other stakeholders must engage in constructive and inclusive dialogue to design the most effective ways to implement these rights in practice.

Figure 1 The programme of the public webinars

participation support social inclusion, creating a new language that, based on art, can engage people. Also, we examined how access remains unequal in many contexts. The session highlighted initiatives that created more inclusive, flexible and meaningful pathways to learning and cultural engagement.

The fourth session, “**Governance and Participation – Policies That Make a Difference**”, addressed how local governments can embed rights into policy through legal, administrative, and financial frameworks. We also explored strategies for involving civil society and marginalised groups in decision-making processes, and discussed the use of social impact evaluation as a tool to assess effectiveness and guide public investment.

The **final session** brought together the project partners to reflect on the thematic sessions conducted throughout the webinars’ series and to identify the key lessons learned. This discussion played a central role in shaping the conclusive remarks presented in the current report.

Each webinar featured contributions from local stakeholders who shared grounded insights and practical experiences. These inputs informed the concluding session on the B.RIGHT SPACES Charter, where participants assessed the Charter’s key messages, identified gaps, and discussed how to strengthen and apply its principles across different territorial contexts.

The participants

The webinars were organised and facilitated by the project partners, who brought together a diverse range of local experiences and perspectives from France, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Spain and Sweden. Each session featured contributions from practitioners and local stakeholders actively engaged in promoting and defending rights in their communities. These voices helped ground the discussions in concrete practice and territorial realities.

In addition, a representative from the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) joined the series, offering an overview of the Agency’s ongoing work to support local and regional policies that protect and promote fundamental rights. This contribution helped connect local practices with the broader European frameworks and priorities.

The presentations are publicly available on the B.RIGHT SPACES project’s website: <https://www.revesnetwork.eu/project/b-right-spaces/>.

The core messages and lessons learned from the B.RIGHT SPACES webinars

1. From Declared Rights to Lived Rights. Making Rights Real

Living Spaces, Living Rights: Civic Hubs at the Heart of Community Transformation

Across European cities, a quiet revolution is reshaping how we think about public space, participation and welfare. It is taking place not in parliaments or press conferences, but in libraries, converted warehouses, cultural centres, and communal kitchens. These are the civic spaces where democracy is not only debated but lived, where shared responsibility, creativity and care are woven into the daily life of neighbourhoods.

The B.RIGHT SPACES first webinar has brought together a wealth of such experiences. Among them, two stand out as particularly inspiring: the *Case del Quartiere* in Turin and the *Miejsca Aktywności Lokalnej* (Local Activity Places, or MAL) in Warsaw.

As cities face mounting social, economic and environmental challenges, civic spaces like *Case del Quartiere* and *MAL* show us a path based on care, collaboration and collective ownership and imagination. They remind us that democracy is not something reserved for election days, but something built day-by-day in the places where we live, learn and meet.

Though they differ in context and approach, both initiatives offer valuable insights into how civic spaces can nurture democratic life from the bottom up.

Casa del Quartiere: Turin's Urban Antennas

In Turin, civic transformation took root in the aftermath of post-industrial decline. Starting in the 1990s, the EU's URBAN initiative helped launch a wave of urban regeneration that reached beyond bricks and mortar to touch the social fabric of neighbourhoods. Out of this emerged the *Case del Quartiere*, or neighbourhood houses, developed not through a top-down mandate, but as organic responses to local needs.

Each *Casa* has its own story, shaped by community initiative and supported by the City of Turin, which later played a key role in helping them connect into a cohesive network. These are not merely spaces for services, instead they are vibrant hubs where culture, learning, commerce, and care converge. Libraries sit alongside coworking areas; music classes happen in rooms once used for storage; a child might learn coding while a grandmother takes a pottery class down the hall.

Far from operating in isolation, the *Case del Quartiere* are governed by a network of second-level associations (local coalitions of civil society groups) and formalised through *Protocolli d'intesa* (Memoranda of Understanding). These are peer-to-peer agreements that allow for collaboration with the city administration without imposing heavy legal obligations. "*Il protocollo è la forma più leggera di accordo che un ente pubblico può firmare, non ha conseguenze politiche o giuridiche, ma crea una cornice*" (The MoU is the lightest form of agreement that a public body can sign, it has no political or legal consequences, but creates a framework), explained one partner. These frameworks support flexibility, trust and autonomy.

Since such spaces are both *place-centred* and *people-centred*, they act as *spaces of mediation* in their communities, where citizens and stakeholders act as local “antennas” picking up signals from the ground and translating them into action.

Perhaps most striking is the emphasis on *beauty as an ordinary feature*. These are not utilitarian spaces designed only for function. These are places of dignity and delight, where accessibility and aesthetics go hand in hand.

MAL: Warsaw’s Network of Everyday Democracy

In Warsaw, the MAL programme has been quietly revolutionising the way public institutions interact with residents. The first MALs were born in 2017, thanks to a modest micro-grant scheme that offered around €7,000 per initiative. This low-barrier funding helped ignite civic energy, with over 110 MALs now spread across the city, each adapted to the unique character of its neighbourhood.

Unlike larger civic centres, MALs are intentionally small-scale, agile and deeply local. Some are hosted in libraries, others in former shops or shared municipal buildings. What unites them is a philosophy of **mutuality and accountability**. Citizens are not passive beneficiaries, but active contributors offering their time, ideas, and skills to co-create the life of the space.

Central to each MAL’s success is the presence of a **coordinator**, that is a *facilitator of relationships*, not just logistics. “Each MAL has a facilitator, a trusted figure, often a person from the neighbourhood itself” shared one Warsaw testimonial. This *human infrastructure* is as vital as the physical one. Coordinators build trust, organise activities and help handle tensions or challenges.

Supported by the City Hall’s Centre for Social Communication, the MALs are formally embedded in Warsaw’s 2030 Strategy and recognised in local policy documents. Their activities range from intergenerational workshops to art therapy, civic advocacy, and even emergency support, such as hosting Ukrainian refugees in 2022. Operating under strict non-commercial and non-partisan principles, they nonetheless serve as laboratories of democratic culture, where civic values are practiced and negotiated every day.

What these Spaces Teach Us

What links Turin’s *Case del Quartiere* and Warsaw’s MALs is more than innovation. It is an ethic of **shared responsibility**, rooted in trust, participation, and care. From these examples, a few key messages emerge:

- **Local rootedness is essential.** Civic spaces work best when they emerge from the ground up. External actors can support, but not substitute, local agency.
- **Flexible collaboration and partnerships enable shared ownership.** Whether through Memoranda of Understanding or other “light” legal frameworks, cities can partner with communities as equals, not superiors.
- **Spaces need both *place* and *people*.** Physical infrastructure is not enough. Coordinators, facilitators and hosts bring spaces to life.
- **Diversity is a strength.** Inclusive, multifunctional spaces serve a wide range of needs, from cultural expression to social support, enriching the community as a whole.

- **Grassroots initiatives deserve long-term support.** Local public authorities should move beyond short-term project funding and invest in daily operations, especially in under-resourced areas.
- **Mutuality builds civic culture.** Participation should not be transactional! Participation should be reciprocal, encouraging citizens and stakeholders to contribute as well as benefit.
- **Collaborative governance enhances resilience.** Civic spaces should include participatory structures (e.g. advisory boards, community assemblies) to guide their direction and ensure accountability.

2. Rights in Peripheral Areas. Local Solutions to Reduce Inequality(ies)

Civic Spaces as Tools for Tackling Inequality: Participation, Trust, and Mutualism in Practice

The second webinar in the B.RIGHT SPACES series addressed how civic spaces, when grounded in trust, autonomy and proximity, can act as powerful infrastructures for tackling systemic inequalities.

It featured insights from two deeply embedded experiences: the association *Créative* in Garges-lès-Gonesse (France) and the Community Spaces Network of Catalonia (Spain).

The “Bus de l’Initiative”

In Garges-lès-Gonesse, a suburb of Paris with high levels of unemployment and socio-economic exclusion, the association **Créative** is working to rebuild the connection between residents, public institutions and social services. In an area where 80% of inhabitants live in subsidized housing and more than 60% are unemployed, traditional outreach and service delivery models have failed to foster trust. In response, *Créative* developed a mobile unit, called the *Bus de l’Initiative*, which visits underserved neighbourhoods to provide on-the-ground access to employment advice, entrepreneurship support, digital tools, and social rights.

This model combines technical assistance with hospitality: outdoor terraces, food and informal set-ups encourage engagement on equal bases.

Crucially, the work is *co-designed* with local associations, informal community leaders and public stakeholders. Preparation is both strategic and relational, involving prior visits, joint planning and multi-actor partnerships. The *Creative Factory*, a stationary hub, complements the mobile service as a site for longer-term accompaniment and project incubation.

The Community Spaces Network

From Catalonia, the experience of the **Community Spaces Network**, coordinated by the Solidarity Economy Network (XES), showcased a different but equally transformative approach. Here, civic spaces are self-managed environments rooted in mutual aid, collective governance and democratic pedagogy. They serve as platforms where communities (often made by migrants, women, and precarious workers) organize to meet needs ranging from food and care to energy, housing and work.

Examples include food cooperatives where payment is anonymous and inclusive; care networks for Alzheimer's patients or single mothers; textile cooperatives led by migrant women; and energy communities sharing solar power among low-income households. *These civic spaces are not simply service hubs, but they are economic and political projects* that address structural inequalities while modelling alternative forms of governance and resource sharing.

The discussion emphasized a shared understanding: in contexts marked by distrust, exclusion and institutional disengagement, **mutuality, accessibility and embeddedness** are at the same time the values and the conditions for any meaningful civic engagement. Participants stressed that public authorities must move from controlling roles to **facilitators and enablers**, providing funding, infrastructure and recognition without compromising autonomy.

What these Spaces Teach Us

- **Trust cannot be restored from a distance.** In Garges-lès-Gonesse, residents do not spontaneously approach institutions. Instead, institutions must come to them, physically, culturally and relationally.
- **Preparation is critical.** Civic engagement starts with careful groundwork: building relationships with local leaders, co-designing actions and communicating clearly before arriving in a community. It is a naïve decision to begin with service delivery!
- **Civic space can also include an economic infrastructure.** The Catalan civic spaces link community self-organization with social economy, enabling self-employment, housing access, food security and care networks through bottom-up entrepreneurship.
- **“Hospitality” is political.** Offering food, informal seating and welcoming atmospheres in mobile and stationary spaces is not superficial, but it helps dismantle hierarchies and makes institutions approachable.
- **Autonomy and co-governance matter.** Self-managed spaces empower marginalized groups to become co-creators of solutions. The role of the public authorities should be to support and enable.
- **Digital exclusion is structural.** As services move online, many residents are left behind. Digital literacy and access must be central to inclusive civic strategies.
- **Spaces must reflect community identities.** From rooftop gardens growing culturally specific foods to co-ops led by migrant women, civic spaces thrive when they respond to local needs and cultural references.
- **Mutual aid builds democratic culture.** Civic spaces function as “schools of democracy” where people learn cooperation, solidarity, and shared responsibility, particularly important where traditional public mechanisms are failing.
- **The state is no longer perceived as neutral.** Participants expressed a growing need for safe, autonomous civic spaces as buffers against political mistrust.
- **Policy must catch up to practice.** Rights are often declared but not enacted. Local public authorities must bridge this gap by resourcing, formalising and co-governing civic spaces that already serve as democratic infrastructures.

3. Education and Culture for All. Accessible and Inclusive Pathways

Civic Spaces, Culture, and Education: Rights in Action

The third webinar in the B.RIGHT SPACES series explored the intersection of civic space, cultural policy and educational practice, placing a strong emphasis on how public institutions, civil society and social economy actors can work together to turn rights into lived realities.

The Messina Community Foundation

The session opened with insights from **Sicily**, where the **Messina Community Foundation** presented a systemic and multi-dimensional approach to territorial development. In one of Europe's most climate-vulnerable and economically fragile regions, the Foundation has built a vibrant ecosystem of partnerships, known as a "cluster," uniting public and private actors across sectors, from social services to energy, finance, research, and the arts. Within this framework, cultural and educational infrastructure is seen as a central lever for regeneration and civic empowerment.

Three sites illustrate this strategy in action.

In **Capo Peloro**, a former military site and neglected landscape has been transformed into a cultural hub with a museum, immersive digital labs, and an annual Mediterranean arts festival, drawing thousands of visitors and engaging local students through artistic workshops.

In **Fondo Saccà**, a historically marginalized shantytown has been partially regenerated, not only through housing but also through the creation of green technology spaces, a nursery, and a library, introducing arts-based education as a pathway out of generational poverty and social isolation.

Finally, in **Provo Valdina**, a rural town facing depopulation, a bio-plastics factory rooted in social economy principles doubles as a design and educational lab, engaging youth, artists, and university partners in co-creating future green jobs.

The Västra Götaland Region human rights-based policies

From **Sweden's Västra Götaland Region**, a different but complementary vision was presented. Here, public institutions have adopted a **human rights-based approach** across regional development policies, especially in culture. An advisory committee on human rights informs and evaluates decisions, working directly with civil society and public service providers.

A standout example comes from the museum sector, where inclusive participation processes led to the development of **Sweden's first permanent exhibition on the Traveller community**, co-curated with community members. The museum also created **digitally accessible cultural heritage sites**, ensuring that age, disability, or distance do not hinder access to culture.

The Comprehensive Municipal Strategy in Torres Vedras

Lastly, **Torres Vedras (Portugal)** showcased a comprehensive municipal strategy grounded in the constitutional recognition of cultural rights. Culture is not treated as a luxury, but as a right integral to democracy and social cohesion. The city's strategic plan for culture was built through broad citizen

engagement and now guides an action-oriented governance platform involving artists, educators, grassroots groups, and the municipality.

This collaborative approach ensures that cultural policy is both rights-based and inclusive. Local initiatives like **Visual Academy**, artistic residencies, and neighbourhood cultural programming demonstrate how youth, migrants, and marginalized groups are actively engaged not only as audiences but as creators.

The city also implements **social impact assessments** for its cultural infrastructure and ensures that mediation and education are embedded across all activities.

What these Spaces Teach Us

- **Culture and education are core components of civic space.** Across all cases, arts and learning are seen not as add-ons, but as foundational to building belonging, equity and participation.
- **Integrated approaches drive systemic change.** The Messina Foundation's ecosystem model demonstrates how housing, sustainability, culture and education can be interwoven into territorial strategies for justice and inclusion.
- **Human rights frameworks offer practical tools.** In Sweden, a rights-based approach anchored in policy, advisory committees and participatory methods, is proving effective in making institutions more inclusive and accountable.
- **Co-creation enhances legitimacy and trust.** In both the museum project in Sweden and urban regeneration in Sicily, communities were not passive beneficiaries but active contributors that shape design, content and outcomes.
- **Civic space as a democratic infrastructure.** Torres Vedras' collaborative governance model shows that municipalities can create structured, inclusive platforms where culture becomes a tool for social connection.
- **Participatory culture policies are feasible and impactful.** With the right frameworks, even small and mid-sized cities can co-design strategies, monitor results and scale inclusive cultural practices across urban and rural areas.
- **Youth and marginalized groups must be central.** Projects like arts-based social initiatives empower youth, migrants and underserved residents ensuring access to cultural creation, not just consumption.
- **Engagement requires time, trust, and mediation.** As seen in the Sicilian context, engaging deeply marginalized populations (e.g., residents in shantytowns) involves long-term dialogue and social mediation, overcoming the natural resistance to innovation.
- **Civic spaces thrive through networks.** All three cases stress the value of cross-sectoral collaboration between public authorities, social economy actors, educators, artists, and citizens, as the engine behind resilient civic infrastructures.

4. Governance and Participation. Policies that Make a Difference

Public Authorities and Civic Spaces: Towards Shared Responsibility

The fourth webinar of the B.RIGHT SPACES project brought into focus the critical role that public authorities play in supporting, protecting, and co-creating civic spaces. As cities and territories across Europe face growing social divides, institutional distrust, and democratic fatigue, the session called attention to a powerful shift in governance: one that repositions citizens not merely as beneficiaries of public policy but as co-authors and co-stewards of the commons.

The Shared Administration of Common Goods and Collaboration Pacts promoted and supported by the Comune di Torino

The session opened with a presentation from Turin, Italy, where the collaborative management of urban commons has become a tested and evolving model. Legal and practical innovations, most notably the “Regulation on Collaboration between Citizens and Administration for the Care and Regeneration of Urban Commons”, have enabled over 300 Italian municipalities to establish more than 7,000 “collaboration pacts”. These pacts institutionalise co-design and co-management processes, recognising citizens as equal partners in shaping and sustaining shared spaces such as gardens, schools, cultural sites, and public buildings.

Turin’s experience, supported by the LABSUS research group, reveals how subsidiarity, legal frameworks and a commitment to co-creation can transform administrative culture and foster new forms of democratic life. By lowering procedural barriers and making participation accessible to individuals, informal groups, and small businesses, the city has empowered a wide spectrum of actors to care for civic spaces in practical, inclusive ways.

The FRA’s Practical Guidance on “Human rights cities in the European Union”

The webinar then moved to a European perspective, with the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) introducing the “Human Rights City” framework. Participation, coherence across municipal departments, and structural accountability were highlighted as core pillars. Cities like Vienna, Utrecht, and Barcelona have adopted formal declarations, created human rights offices, and built participatory tools, such as youth councils and neighbourhood consultations, to operationalise rights at the local level. FRA’s work underscores the value of aligning local governance with fundamental rights through strategic frameworks, EU Charter commitments, and capacity-building across all levels of the administration.

The Initiatives of the Città Metropolitana di Roma Capitale

The Metropolitan City of Rome shared its approach as a coordinating authority for over 120 municipalities. Through initiatives such as the *Metropolitan Tables for Coexistence* and digital participation platforms, Rome seeks to connect fragmented civic energies, empower local networks, and co-create inclusive regulation frameworks—including one for foreign residents. Projects like *Insieme Siamo Arte* and *Viaggiare nel Sociale* illustrate how culture, care, and participation can intersect across vast and diverse territories.

Public policies for a new democratic paradigm in Catalonia

From Catalonia, the regional government presented a policy architecture rooted in community-led economies and social solidarity. Amidst rising authoritarian and exclusionary narratives, Catalonia places the defence of civic spaces at the heart of democratic renewal. Its forthcoming law on the social and solidarity economy, participatory budgeting tools, and new programs like *Comunares* are intended to formalise and scale community self-organisation, backed by institutional recognition and financial support.

Crucially, Catalan representatives emphasized the need for a fourfold enabling environment:

- legal recognition,
- administrative simplification,
- sustained public funding, and
- conceptual empowerment of citizens.

This means ensuring participation is not a rhetorical gesture but a right grounded in practice, infrastructure, and inclusive language.

The dialogue concluded with a collective reflection: building participatory governance and resilient civic spaces is not simply a technical task. It requires deep institutional shifts, emotional and political commitment, and cross-sector alliances. Whether through constitutional subsidiarity, human rights frameworks, or cooperative economies, the path forward lies in embedding participation at the heart of governance.

What these Spaces Teach Us

- **Civic space is co-governance in action.** Turin’s “collaboration pacts” show how formal agreements between citizens and local administrations can democratise public space management and redefine public authority as a partner rather than a gatekeeper.
- **Participation must be structurally supported.** Whether through a human rights office, participatory councils, or municipal charters, effective participation relies on institutional structures, not just good intentions.
- **Legal innovation enables social transformation.** Italy’s constitutional principle of horizontal subsidiarity has served as a legal foundation for empowering bottom-up civic initiatives across multiple municipalities.
- **Human rights cities offer a replicable model.** The FRA’s Human Rights City framework provides cities with tools to embed rights-based approaches across governance, strengthen participation, and secure continuity beyond political cycles.
- **Administrative culture needs transformation.** Both Catalonia and Turin emphasized that civil servants must be trained, supported, and involved from the outset. Participation must be understood and valued inside institutions not just managed from the outside.
- **Finance and flexibility go hand-in-hand.** Civic spaces need stable, accessible funding beyond short-term projects. Co-created policies also demand flexible administrative processes that adapt to community realities.

- **Digital and physical access must be inclusive.** Ensuring participatory tools (such as portals like *Decidim*) are accessible across language, digital literacy and geographic lines is key to inclusive civic engagement.
- **Public authorities as enablers, not managers.** Whether through supporting community economies in Catalonia or building trust through mobile units in Rome, public institutions should provide infrastructure and protection while respecting autonomy.
- **Shared responsibility strengthens democracy.** Civic participation is not about consultation alone... it is about mutual ownership of problems, policies and possibilities.

Conclusive remarks

The B.RIGHT SPACES webinar series has offered an interesting insight into how civic spaces – whether initiated by public institutions, community actors or cooperative networks – are actively (re)shaping democratic life across European territories. These spaces, far from being peripheral or symbolic, are strategic infrastructures where rights take shape, inequalities are addressed and new forms of governance emerge.

For local authorities and stakeholders, the challenge is not only to acknowledge the transformative role of civic spaces but to embed them structurally into the public policy ecosystem.

The following strategic directions draw on the lived experiences presented in the webinars, and aim to inform a shift toward more collaborative, inclusive and resilient local governance.

<p>Civic spaces as democratic infrastructure</p>	<p><i>Local public policy must treat civic spaces as more than service hubs, but as platforms for rights implementation, democratic learning and collective care.</i> <i>Planning instruments, urban development frameworks and cultural strategies should formally include civic spaces as core elements of public infrastructure, on par with schools, libraries and parks.</i></p>
<p>Civic co-governance should be embedded in local legal and institutional frameworks</p>	<p><i>From collaboration pacts in Turin to Torres Vedras' participatory cultural councils, policy should enable shared governance models that give communities a formal role in shaping, managing and evaluating civic initiatives. Instruments such as memoranda of understanding, co-design processes and citizens' boards should be scaled and adapted to local contexts.</i></p>
<p>Shift the role of institutions: from providers to enablers</p>	<p><i>Local governments must evolve from service providers to ecosystem enablers, offering stability, resources and protection while respecting the autonomy of civic actors.</i> <i>This includes recognising self-managed spaces, supporting non-institutional forms of organisation and facilitating cross-sector collaboration without imposing top-down control</i></p>
<p>Secure long-term, flexible funding</p>	<p><i>Civic spaces require more than project-based grants. Policies must ensure core funding for operational costs (i.e., staff, maintenance, and utilities) especially in disadvantaged areas.</i> <i>Diverse financial instruments should be explored, including participatory budgeting, community-led grant-making and multi-year funding agreements to reduce precarity and enable long-term planning.</i></p>
<p>Strengthen human infrastructure</p>	<p><i>Facilitators, coordinators, cultural mediators and other profiles are the human anchors of civic space.</i> <i>Local policies should invest in training, professional recognition and peer learning for these roles. Supporting local leadership within communities is as vital as investing in physical space.</i></p>
<p>Equity through accessible design and inclusive language</p>	<p><i>Civic spaces must be designed and governed with accessibility in mind (digitally, physically and culturally).</i> <i>Policies should require inclusive communication practices, language diversity and universal design standards, ensuring that migrants, youth, older adults and marginalised communities can all participate meaningfully</i></p>

<p>Civic spaces as laboratories for innovation and justice</p>	<p><i>Civic spaces can serve as testing grounds for social innovation, piloting approaches to care, employment, housing, sustainability and education. Local authorities should create regulatory “safe zones” where experimentation is supported, evaluated and scaled, especially in contexts of crisis or rapid change</i></p>
<p>Participatory evaluation and policy feedback loops</p>	<p><i>Monitoring and evaluation must move beyond quantitative metrics. Local policies should adopt participatory evaluation tools that value storytelling, community feedback and qualitative outcomes. Civic actors should be involved not only in delivering services, but in shaping how success is defined and measured</i></p>
<p>Civic space strategy aligned with broader territorial objectives</p>	<p><i>Civic space policy should not exist in isolation. It must be integrated into broader urban, rural, and metropolitan strategies, linking to agendas on climate resilience, education, social inclusion, digital transition, economic development, etc. Cross-departmental coordination within municipalities is key to ensuring coherence and impact</i></p>
<p>Protect autonomy and guard against co-optation</p>	<p><i>The autonomy of civic actors must be safeguarded. Local policy must resist the temptation to institutionalise creativity or co-opt dissent. Instead, municipalities should see civic spaces as partners with different roles, timelines and logics, as a pre-requisite for a pluralistic and healthy democracy</i></p>